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MASTER'S THESIS

EMPLOYING LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS FOR SYSTEMATIC EXTRACTION OF NANOPARTICLE DESIGNS FROM SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE

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**Master's Degree in Intelligent Systems (MUSI)
Specialization in Computer Vision & Data Science.**

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Employing Large Language Models for Systematic Extraction of Nanoparticle Designs from Scientific Literature

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Abstract—The fast-paced growth of scientific literature hinders the efficient extraction of structured data, particularly in nanomedicine where nanoparticle (NP) design details are essential for developing blood-brain barrier (BBB)–penetrating therapies designed for use in Central Nervous System (CNS)–related disorders. This thesis introduces an automated pipeline that leverages open-weight Large Language Models (LLMs) for the extraction of NP design information from scientific articles into a structured predefined taxonomy.

A corpus of 528 papers covering six BBB-targeting NP types was compiled from PubMed, PubMed Central, and Europe PMC. Preprocessing included OCR for PDFs and XML parsing. Three LLMs—Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct, Qwen3 32B, and Gemma3 27B-it—were prompted in a zero-shot setting to generate structured JSON outputs. A judge model, MedGemma 27B-text-it, harmonized these outputs. Evaluation against a 50-paper manually annotated gold standard considered schema conformance, exact match accuracy (numerical, categorical), BERTScore (free-text), and F1-scores (null-handling).

All models achieved high schema conformance (>0.99). Mistral Small 3.1 Instruct performed best on PDF-derived numerical data (0.722 exact match), while Qwen3 32B achieved the highest performance on XML content (0.667). PDF-derived data showed higher error (MAE/RMSE 10^9 – 10^{11}) than XML (<25), mainly due to OCR challenges. MedGemma improved semantic similarity (BERT F1 up to 0.644) and null-handling (F1 up to 0.861), although not always outperforming individual models in exact match metrics.

These results demonstrate the feasibility of open-weight LLMs for automated NP data extraction in neurotherapeutics. While promising, performance remains sensitive to input quality, especially from PDFs, and human oversight is still needed for high-stakes applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The accelerating pace of scientific publications poses an increasing challenge for researchers in data-intensive fields [5]. In nanomedicine, the volume of publications has surged, with thousands of new articles added daily to repositories such as PubMed [21]. A prominent application area is the development of nanoparticles (NPs) capable of delivering drugs by penetrating the blood-brain barrier (BBB), a vital physiological defense that complicates treatment of central nervous system (CNS) disorders [15, 33].

Effective development of BBB-targeted nanotherapies requires access to detailed, structured data on NP design parameters such as core material, particle size, surface modifications

(e.g., PEGylation, ligands), and experimental models [33]. However, this crucial information is typically buried within unstructured scientific texts, reported inconsistently across publications, and scattered over vast volumes of literature [3, 30]. This lack of accessible, structured design data hinders knowledge synthesis, slows innovation, and increases redundancy in experimental research [26].

While systematic reviews (SRs) can help extract and organize such data, they are time-consuming and labor-intensive, often taking months to complete [10, 29]. Existing automation tools generally fall short: rule-based approaches often lack domain adaptability, and traditional machine learning methods typically require extensive labeled datasets and struggle with complex, nested biomedical relationships [10]. This disconnect between available information and usable knowledge represents a significant bottleneck in nanomedicine research [1]. Addressing this need requires advanced natural language understanding capable of interpreting domain-specific terminology, implicit relations, and diverse reporting styles to accelerate drug delivery research across the BBB, enable faster meta-analyses, data-driven hypothesis generation, and more effective design of new NPs.

Advances in Large Language Models (LLMs)—including Claude, LLaMA, and GPT-4—have significantly advanced the automated extraction of scientific information. Built upon the transformer architecture, these models have proven effective in natural language processing (NLP) applications, including the extraction of entities (NER) and the identification of relations between them (RE), often requiring minimal labeled data through techniques involving prompt design and limited-example (few-shot) learning [4, 6]. Additionally, LLMs can generate structured outputs (e.g., JSON, tables), which makes them well suited for building end-to-end pipelines that convert raw literature into analyzable data [18]. Their application to scientific literature mining is still emerging but particularly promising in under-resourced domains like nanomedicine [7], offering a timely opportunity to automate the extraction of structured nanoparticle design data from scientific publications and reduce reliance on time-consuming manual reviews.

A. Thesis Objective and Research Aims

The objective of this thesis is to design, implement, and evaluate a computational pipeline that uses LLMs to extract structured information on nanoparticle design from scientific publications, with a specific focus on formulations intended for the targeting of the BBB. This research work focuses on developing a methodological framework capable of identifying and organizing key design features reported in the literature.

The pipeline will focus on extracting, but is not limited to, the following nanoparticle attributes:

- Core material(s)
- Physicochemical properties such as size, shape and surface charge
- Surface modifications (e.g., PEGylation, targeting ligands)
- Biological targets or transport mechanisms
- Encapsulated agents (e.g., drugs, imaging compounds)
- Experimental models (e.g., in vitro BBB models, animal studies)

To achieve this objective, the thesis will pursue the following research aims:

- **Taxonomy Development:** Construct a structured taxonomy of nanoparticle design parameters, informed by a review of existing literature and relevant biomedical ontologies.
- **Pipeline Architecture:** Develop a modular LLM-based pipeline that encompasses literature retrieval, preprocessing, nanoparticle design information extraction, and output structuring.
- **Performance Evaluation:** Assess the pipeline's effectiveness using standard NLP metrics (e.g., precision, recall, F1-score), and compare the capabilities of the different LLMs and approaches used.

B. Scope of this thesis work

This thesis is part of the "Non-Animal Platform for Nanoparticle-Based Delivery across the blood-brain barrier Interface with Vehicle Evolution" (NAP4DIVE) project, which aims to replace animal models with a machine learning-based simulator which evaluates thousands of literature-proposed nanoparticle designs and predicts the most promising ones to be selected for drug development. This thesis therefore, focuses on the automated extraction of nanoparticle design information from English-language scientific literature, primarily full-text research articles indexed in PubMed to be used in the development of the ML-based simulator. The scope is restricted to nanoparticle formulations specifically developed for the penetration of the BBB in therapeutic or diagnostic contexts. As such, this work does not address the experimental synthesis, in vivo validation, or clinical evaluation of nanoparticles.

Crucially, the selection of inclusion criteria, nanoparticle classes, and relevant therapeutic applications was carried out in close collaboration with domain experts in nanomedicine and BBB research. These experts played an active role in informing the design of the corpus, validating key assumptions,

and guiding the relevance of the extracted information to the broader goals of the NAP4DIVE project.

This research lays the groundwork for future computational tools aimed at accelerating knowledge synthesis in nanomedicine and enhancing the efficiency and reproducibility of nanoparticle design. The core innovation presented in this work is the development and evaluation of an open-weight LLM-based pipeline tailored for this specific, complex extraction task.

This thesis is organized into the following sections: Section II provides a background on traditional and contemporary approaches to scientific information extraction, highlighting the gaps addressed by this work. Section III details the research design, data collection and preprocessing methods, the architecture of the LLM-based extraction framework, and the evaluation strategy. Section IV presents the quantitative results from the pipeline's performance evaluation. Section V provides an interpretation of the results, examines their significance and limitations. Lastly, Section VI highlights the main findings, contributions presented in this thesis, and outlines potential avenues for future research.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

While Section I established the challenges in extracting structured nanoparticle (NP) design data for BBB applications and introduced Large Language Models (LLMs) as a promising solution, this section provides a thorough review of existing literature. It examines prior approaches to scientific information extraction and the specific applications of LLMs, thereby identifying the research gaps this thesis aims to address.

A. Prior Approaches to Scientific Information Extraction

Initial attempts at scientific information extraction have largely relied on rule-based systems and traditional machine learning approaches. These methods demonstrated modest success (48% – 64%) in extracting structured metadata, such as authorship or simple named entities, but struggled with more complex and context-dependent relational information typical of experimental science [14]. In chemistry and materials science, tools such as ChemicalTagger, ChemDataExtractor, and CERMINE provided structured outputs based on predefined templates or grammar-based rules [22]. However, these systems often required domain-specific customization and lacked scalability.

In the biomedical field, early biological named entity recognition (BNER) systems demonstrated reliable identification of entities such as proteins or genes, but often required extensive annotated corpora for training [16]. Although some success was achieved using these tools in narrow biomedical subdomains, they proved insufficient for extracting the multifaceted parameters associated with nanoparticle design, which often involves implicit relationships between core material, ligands, and biological function. These limitations underscore the need for more advanced techniques.

B. Large Language Models in Scientific and Biomedical Data Extraction

LLMs have recently revolutionized the field of text-based scientific information extraction. Their capabilities span a broad spectrum of applications, including extraction of relevant information from a biomedical corpus, without task-specific training, by leveraging zero-shot learning paradigms [11]. In chemical and materials science, LLMs have enabled the development of domain-specific extraction pipelines that bypass traditional machine learning bottlenecks, including the need for large annotated datasets or complex feature engineering. For example, Schilling-Wilhelmi et al. [24] described a full workflow for chemical data extraction using LLMs, from raw PDF ingestion to structured table generation. Similarly, Rettenberger et al. [23] demonstrated an LLM-based system for extracting experimental synthesis parameters of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) from full-text articles. These pipelines often involve iterative summarization, contextual windowing, and prompt engineering to accommodate token limits and ensure information integrity.

In the domain of biomedical literature synthesis, LLMs have shown promise in supporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses. Schmidt et al. [25] investigated the feasibility of employing GPT-4 for semi-automated data extraction in systematic reviews across human, animal, and social science domains. They reported moderate accuracy (72–82%) with notable variability depending on study design complexity and data granularity. The most challenging aspects were the extraction of experimental methods and outcomes—elements directly relevant to nanoparticle formulation and evaluation.

Despite these advances, challenges persist with LLMs. Context fragmentation, implicit semantic relationships, and inconsistent reporting styles continue to limit performance. Even sophisticated LLMs suffer from hallucinations, which can introduce spurious or misleading information [2]. Domain-specific fine-tuning and the use of hybrid models—combining LLMs with curated dictionaries or ontologies—have been proposed to mitigate these limitations [8]. Recent efforts have also explored strategies such as fine-tuning and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to improve LLMs effectiveness on long-context scientific synthesis tasks [2], offering potential solutions for multi-document reasoning.

C. Gaps in Nanoparticle Design Extraction for BBB Applications

Despite progress in chemical and biomedical information extraction, very few studies have addressed the systematic extraction of nanoparticle design parameters—especially in the specific context of BBB targeting. The only closely related effort involved LLM-assisted extraction of synthesis protocols for gold nanoparticles, which did not address biological targets, transport mechanisms, or experimental validation models [17]. Most current studies extract limited subsets of data (e.g., bulk modulus, ligand names, or reaction conditions) without relational linking or context-aware inference.

In addition, few pipelines are optimized for resource-constrained environments. Most require proprietary LLMs or

extensive computational infrastructure, limiting their utility for open-source, lightweight deployments. The lack of domain-specific benchmarks or annotated corpora in nanomedicine exacerbates the problem, impeding systematic evaluation and reproducibility.

D. Novelty and Positioning of the Present Work

This thesis addresses these limitations by presenting a modular, open-source LLM pipeline for extracting structured, multivariate design information on nanoparticles engineered for BBB penetration. The proposed system is novel in three key ways: (1) its focus on extracting comprehensive design profiles—including material composition, surface chemistry, and biological validation methods—from full-length biomedical papers; (2) its adaptation to operate with open-weight LLMs deployable on consumer-grade hardware; and (3) its emphasis on the neurotherapeutic application domain, which remains largely unrepresented in current literature mining initiatives.

In doing so, this research bridges important gaps in automated knowledge extraction for nanomedicine, offering a reproducible and scalable framework for accelerating scientific synthesis and hypothesis generation in BBB-targeted nanoparticle design. It aims to provide a foundational methodology and performance baseline for future development in this specialized area.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section explains the structured methodology adopted to achieve the objectives of the thesis: the design, implementation, and evaluation of a computational pipeline employing LLMs for the extraction of nanoparticle design parameters from scientific literature. The methodology is structured to address each research objective, which includes data collection, preprocessing, the LLM-based information extraction framework, and the proposed evaluation strategy. Figure 1 illustrates the complete architecture of the end-to-end pipeline, providing a visual summary of the main components and their interactions.

A. Research Design and Approach

This research follows a developmental and evaluative research design. The primary goal is the development of a novel computational pipeline for automated information extraction from a specialized domain—nanoparticle design for BBB penetration. The approach is predominantly quantitative, focusing on the extraction of structured data and the subsequent evaluation of the pipeline’s performance using established metrics.

The nature of this study is developmental, involving the implementation of a new computational pipeline, and evaluative, through the assessment of its performance and a comparison of different configurations, such as the choice of LLM and data aggregation strategies. Although the methodology is presented in a linear fashion for clarity, the actual development of such a pipeline, particularly with respect to prompt engineering

Figure 1. End-to-end architecture of the proposed LLM-based information extraction pipeline for nanoparticle design parameters from scientific literature. The pipeline begins with the collection of full-text articles from biomedical databases (PubMed, PMC, Europe PMC), followed by preprocessing to extract and clean content into a unified Markdown format. A context-length check determines whether the input text exceeds the LLM’s context window. If so, the text is split into overlapping chunks, each processed independently by the selected large language models (Mistral-Small-3.1-24B-Instruct-2503, Qwen3 32B, Gemma3 27B) using a zero-shot prompting strategy. Chunk-level outputs are aggregated using either a rule-based (first non-null) or LLM-based merging strategy. For shorter texts, extraction is performed directly without chunking or aggregation. Each model produces a structured JSON output representing the extracted design parameters. A dedicated judge model (MedGemma 27B) harmonizes the outputs from the three LLMs into a single consolidated result. Final outputs are evaluated against a gold standard corpus of 50 manually annotated papers using schema conformance, null-handling F1 score, and content-based metrics including BERTScore, MAE, and RMSE. Both harmonized and unharmonized outputs are evaluated to assess model reliability and aggregation effectiveness.

and the selection of optimal LLM strategies, involved an iterative refinement process. The initial choices for prompts or aggregation techniques were systematically adjusted on the basis of preliminary observations and tests to enhance extraction quality. This iterative refinement is inherent in the development of novel computational systems, especially those utilizing the advanced reasoning capabilities of LLMs. The inclusion of a "judge" model, for instance, arose from the recognized need for an additional layer of refinement beyond the primary extraction phase, a requirement often identified during such developmental cycles. This iterative approach, rooted in a pragmatic paradigm, seeks to create a functional and useful tool for researchers in nanomedicine while simultaneously contributing to a broader understanding of LLM capabilities in specialized scientific domains.

B. Data Collection and Corpus Curation

A focused corpus of scientific literature was assembled to serve as the main source of data for the LLM-based extraction task. The collection process was guided by specific criteria to

ensure relevance to the scope of the investigation, with the aim of building a dataset that is both targeted and comprehensive enough for the development and initial validation of the extraction pipeline.

1) *Literature Search Strategy*: The primary sources for literature retrieval were comprehensive biomedical databases: PubMed, PubMed Central (PMC), and Europe PMC. These databases were selected for their extensive coverage of peer-reviewed literature in nanomedicine and related biomedical fields, offering access to full-text articles or, at minimum, detailed abstracts essential for assessing relevance before attempting full-text retrieval for information extraction.

The inclusion criteria for documents in the corpus were precisely defined to align with the thesis objectives:

- **Nanoparticle Focus**: Scientific papers centered on one or more of the following six nanoparticle types: Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles (MSNs), Extracellular Vesicles (EVs), Lipid Nanoparticles (LNPs), Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), Polymeric Micelles (PMs), and Spherical Nucleic Acids (SNAs). These types were chosen due to their prominence in the research on BBB

penetration and their alignment with the NAP4DIVE project.

- **Therapeutic Application Context:** Studies investigating the potential of these nanoparticles to traverse the BBB for the treatment or diagnosis of a specified list of neurological and CNS conditions: Alzheimer’s disease, neuro-degenerative diseases, brain tumors / brain cancer, central nervous system (CNS) diseases, Parkinson’s disease, dementia, Glioblastoma, Huntington’s disease, and schizophrenia.
- **Article Type:** Full-text research articles were prioritized to ensure sufficient detail on nanoparticle design, synthesis, characterization, and experimental validation of BBB penetration. Abstracts, reviews, and meta-analyses, while potentially useful for context, were generally excluded as primary sources for data extraction.
- **Language:** Publications were included in the corpus only if they were written in English.
- **Publication Date:** Only articles published in 2010 or later were considered, with the vast majority (over 80%) of selected papers published within the last five years (2020 onwards), ensuring that the dataset reflects current research trends and methodologies.

The search query formulation involved constructing Boolean search strings combining keywords related to the specified nanoparticle types (e.g., "Lipid Nanoparticles," "Extracellular Vesicles"), disease names (e.g., "Alzheimer’s disease," "glioblastoma"), and terms indicative of BBB interaction (e.g., "BBB," "blood-brain barrier," "brain delivery," "CNS delivery"). The high specificity of these criteria was intended to create a very targeted corpus, which is advantageous for developing a specialized extraction model, as it allows for the formulation of precise extraction prompts tailored to this niche. However, it is acknowledged that this specificity implies that the pipeline’s performance metrics and any learned textual patterns might not directly generalize to other nanoparticle types or disease contexts without further adaptation or evaluation.

2) *Data Retrieval Process:* The retrieval of relevant scientific papers involved both automated and manual methods, reflecting the practical challenges of accessing full-text scientific literature.

- **Automated Retrieval:** A significant portion of the corpus was retrieved programmatically using the `Entrez` Programming Utility from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). This tool allowed for efficient querying of PubMed and PubMed Central databases based on the defined search strategy, facilitating the download of available open-access full-text articles or XML versions.
- **Manual Retrieval:** A substantial number of papers required manual retrieval. This was primarily necessitated by institutional access requirements and publisher paywalls that prevented automated download of full-text articles, even when abstracts or metadata indicated high relevance. In these cases, papers were accessed via university library subscriptions or other legitimate institutional channels and downloaded individually.

The distribution of the papers retrieved across the targeted nanoparticle types, detailing the count from automated versus manual retrieval, is presented in Table I. The total corpus comprised 528 articles. The reliance on manual retrieval (386 papers, 73.1% of the total) over automated methods (142 papers, 26.9%) underscores a notable practical challenge in literature-based computational research. For certain categories, such as Lipid Nanoparticles (145 manual vs. 14 automatic), this disparity was particularly stark. This heavy dependence on manual processes highlights systemic issues in scientific knowledge dissemination, primarily related to access restrictions, which can impact the scalability and reproducibility of research relying on large-scale literature analysis. It also signifies a considerable time investment in the corpus creation phase of this project. Although manual selection was guided by strict relevance criteria based on abstracts and titles before attempting full download, the necessity for manual access was predominantly an issue of accessibility rather than initial identification.

3) *Ethical Considerations and Data Usage:* All literature included in the corpus was sourced from publicly accessible databases or through institutional subscriptions available to the researcher. The research adheres to fair use principles for text mining of copyrighted materials. The focus is strictly on the extraction of factual data points and insights related to nanoparticle design for academic research purposes. There is no intention to reproduce or redistribute full-text copyrighted content. The primary aim is the advancement of scientific knowledge and the development of tools to aid scientific discovery within the nanomedicine community.

C. Data Preprocessing

To prepare the collected scientific articles for effective processing by LLMs, a multi-step preprocessing pipeline was implemented. This pipeline was designed to convert heterogeneous document formats into a unified plain text representation (Markdown) and subsequently to clean this text by removing sections less likely to contain the targeted nanoparticle design information, thereby optimizing the input for the LLM extraction stage.

1) *Format Conversion and Text Extraction:* The retrieved research papers were available exclusively in PDF and XML formats. Distinct strategies were employed for each format to ensure maximal information recovery in a consistent textual format.

- **PDF Document Processing:** For papers obtained in PDF format, `Mistral` OCR was employed. This Optical Character Recognition engine was selected owing to its demonstrated high accuracy and robustness in handling the complex layouts, multi-column structures, and embedded figures and tables typical of scientific publications [19]. The PDFs were converted directly into Markdown format. Markdown was chosen as the standardized intermediate representation due to its lightweight nature, human readability, and its ability to preserve basic structural elements (such as headings and lists) which can be implicitly useful for LLMs, while being fundamentally a plain text format easily parsable by downstream tools.

Table I
SUMMARY OF RETRIEVED SCIENTIFIC PAPERS BY NANOPARTICLE TYPE AND RETRIEVAL METHOD

Nanoparticle Type	Automatic Retrieval	Manual Retrieval	Total
Extracellular Vesicles	68	97	165
Lipid Nanoparticles	14	145	159
Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles	16	24	40
Metal–Organic Frameworks	9	11	20
Polymeric Micelles	32	93	125
Spherical Nucleic Acids	3	16	19
Total	142	386	528

- **XML Document Processing:** For documents available in XML format, often originating from PubMed Central’s open access subset which frequently uses the Journal Article Tag Suite (JATS) DTD, a custom Python script was developed. The relatively consistent structure of these XML files made it feasible to write a targeted script for content extraction. This script parsed the XML trees to extract relevant textual content from sections such as the abstract, discussion, introduction, materials and methods, and results, and then converted this extracted content into the same Markdown format used for PDF-derived texts.

The decision to standardize all documents to Markdown was important. This ensured that all subsequent processing steps, including cleaning, chunking, and input preparation for the LLMs, could operate on a uniform data type, significantly simplifying the overall pipeline architecture and reducing the complexity of managing different input formats.

2) *Content Cleaning:* Following conversion to Markdown, each document underwent a further preprocessing step. This involved programmatically identifying and removing sections deemed less relevant for the specific task of extracting nanoparticle design parameters.

The sections targeted for removal included:

- References and Bibliographies (e.g., “References”, “Bibliography”, “Literature Cited”, “Cited Works”)
- Conflict of Interest and Declaration Statements (e.g., “Conflict of Interest”, “Competing Interests”, “COI Statement”, “Disclosure Statement”)
- Ethics-Related Sections (e.g., “Ethics Statement”, “Ethical Considerations”, “Ethical Approval”, “Ethics Committee”)
- Acknowledgements and Funding Information (e.g., “Acknowledgments”, “Funding”, “Grants”, “Financial Support”, “Financial Disclosure”)
- Supplementary Material and Appendices (e.g., “Supplementary Information”, “Appendix”, “Supporting Information”)
- Title and Author Sections (e.g., “Title”, “Authors”, “Affiliations”, “Author Contributions”, “Corresponding Author”)
- Miscellaneous Non-Core Sections (e.g., “Copyright”, “Data Availability”, “Code Availability”, “Abbreviations”, “Keywords”, “Limitations”, “Future Work”)

The rationale for removing these sections was twofold: firstly, they typically do not contain primary information about nanoparticle design parameters such as core material, particle size, surface modifications, or BBB permeability data.

Secondly, their inclusion can introduce substantial noise, increase the overall document length unnecessarily (potentially exceeding LLM context windows or requiring more aggressive chunking), and dilute the focus of the extraction process.

The objective of this cleaning phase was to produce more concise documents containing primarily the core scientific narrative (typically found in the Methods, Results, and Discussion sections) where nanoparticle design details are most likely to be explicitly reported. This targeted approach aimed to optimize the input for the LLMs, increasing their ability to locate relevant information efficiently. This strategy involves a trade-off: while it reduces noise and processing load, there is a small, acknowledged risk of discarding relevant information if, in rare cases, crucial design details were exclusively located within these removed sections (e.g., a specific material detailed only in an appendix). However, the assumption is that primary design parameters are predominantly reported in the main body of scientific articles.

D. Taxonomy of Nanoparticle Design Parameters

As indicated in Section I-A, an important preliminary step, preceding the development of the LLM extraction mechanism, was the construction of a structured taxonomy of nanoparticle design parameters. This taxonomy served as the conceptual blueprint for the information extraction task, defining the specific fields of interest and the desired schema for the structured output.

The taxonomy was developed through an iterative process involving:

- A comprehensive review of existing literature in nanomedicine, with a particular focus on studies involving nanoparticles designed for BBB targeting.
- Consultation of relevant biomedical ontologies and established classification systems where applicable, to ensure alignment with standard terminologies.
- Expert input to refine the scope and granularity of the parameters.

The resulting taxonomy defines the complete set of parameters for the extraction pipeline. Each field, its detailed description, and its applicability across the various nanoparticle types are presented in Table II.

This taxonomy is foundational to the entire methodology. It directly informs the design of the prompts used for the LLMs and defines the keys for the structured JSON objects that the pipeline aims to produce. The quality, clarity, and comprehensiveness of this taxonomy are therefore paramount, as they directly determine the relevance, utility, and interpretability

Table II

THE STRUCTURED TAXONOMY OF NANOPARTICLE DESIGN PARAMETERS. THIS TABLE OUTLINES ALL UNIQUE FIELDS DEFINED FOR THE INFORMATION EXTRACTION TASK, THEIR DESCRIPTIONS, AND THEIR APPLICABILITY ACROSS THE DIFFERENT NANOPARTICLE TYPES.

Parameter	Description	Applicable To
Acute Toxicity	Data on the immediate toxic effects of nanoparticles following short-term exposure, often measured using assays like LD50 (lethal dose for 50% of the population). Example: LD50 value of 100.	All
Agglomeration / aggregation	Information on the extent to which nanoparticles cluster together. This can include measurements like aggregation size (nm) or descriptive terms (e.g., high aggregation, low aggregation).	All
Aqueous Degradability/Water Degradability	Indicates how nanoparticles degrade in water. This can be represented as a degradation rate (e.g., percentage per hour) or descriptive terms (e.g., highly degradable, non-degradable).	SNAs, PMs, LNPs, EVs
Chronic toxicity	Data on the long-term toxic effects of nanoparticles following prolonged exposure, often measured using chronic toxicity assays. Example: chronic exposure results indicating organ-specific toxicity.	All
Crystal order (for MSNs: pore ordering)	Information on the crystalline structure of nanoparticles. This can include descriptions of crystal phases (e.g., cubic, hexagonal) or numerical values related to crystallinity (e.g., degree of crystallinity). For MSNs, this refers to the pore structure order.	MSNs
Developmental toxicity	Data on the impact of nanoparticles on the development of organisms, including measurements from developmental toxicity assays. Example: incidence of developmental abnormalities.	All
Experience with human exposure	Descriptions and quantitative data related to human exposure to nanoparticles, including exposure levels and observed effects. Example: exposure concentration in mg/m ³ .	All
Explosivity	Data on the explosive potential of nanoparticles, including explosive limits and conditions. Example: explosive concentration range in %.	All
Flammability	Information on the flammability of nanoparticles, including ignition temperature and flammability ratings. Example: ignition temperature in °C.	All
Genetic toxicity	Information on the potential of nanoparticles to cause genetic damage, assessed using tests like the Ames test or comet assay. Example: frequency of mutations per cell.	All
Immunotoxicity	Information on the adverse effects of nanoparticles on the immune system, often measured using specific assays (e.g., cytokine release assay). Example: levels of cytokines in pg/mL.	All
Integrity	Measures of the structural integrity of nanoparticles, often assessed through stability tests or mechanical strength measurements. Example: percentage of intact particles after a stress test.	EVs
Material composition	Description of particle constituents.	All
Methods of production	Descriptions of the methods used to produce nanoparticles, such as chemical vapor deposition, sol-gel process, or ball milling.	All
Monodispersity (Homogeneity)	Indicates the uniformity of particle sizes within a sample. It can be represented as a numerical value (e.g., polydispersity index) or a descriptive term (e.g., monodisperse, polydisperse).	All
Morphology	Descriptions of the nanoparticle's shape and structure, such as spherical, rod-like, cubic, etc.	All
Nano material name	General name of nanomaterial.	All
Particle Concentration	The number of nanoparticles per unit volume of solution or dispersion, often measured in particles per milliliter (particles/mL).	EVs
Particle number	The count of nanoparticles in a given volume or sample.	All
Particle size distribution	Measurements indicating the range and distribution of particle sizes within a sample. This can include numerical values (e.g., mean size, standard deviation) and descriptive terms (e.g., monodisperse, polydisperse).	All
Permeability	Potential to traverse the BBB.	All
Pharmacokinetics (ADME)	Refers to information on how nanoparticles are absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and excreted in biological systems. This can include numerical values (e.g., half-life, clearance rate) and descriptive terms.	All
Presence of typical EV markers	Information on the presence of extracellular vesicle (EV) markers, often determined through specific assays. Example: presence of CD63, CD81 markers.	EVs
Repeated dose toxicity	Information on the toxic effects of nanoparticles following repeated exposure over a period of time. Example: No Observed Adverse Effect Level (NOAEL) value of 10 mg/kg/day.	All
Reproductive toxicity	Information on the adverse effects of nanoparticles on reproductive health, often measured using specific assays (e.g., fertility tests, teratogenicity studies). Example: percentage of affected offspring.	All
Storage stability	Information on how well nanoparticles maintain their properties over time under various storage conditions. This can include numerical values (e.g., stability duration in months) and descriptive terms (e.g., stable at room temperature).	All
Surface chemistry	Information on functional groups or coatings present on the nanoparticle surface, such as PEGylation or other chemical modifications.	All
Targeting	Information on the targeting mechanisms of nanoparticles that involve ligand-mediated uptake. This can include: String: Descriptions of the ligands used for targeting (e.g., antibodies, peptides). Assay: Results from assays that measure the efficiency of ligand-mediated uptake (e.g., binding affinity assays, cellular uptake assays). Number: Quantitative data such as binding affinities (e.g., K _d values), percentage of uptake by target cells.	SNAs, MSNs, MOFs, PMs, LNPs
Targeting(EV)	surface proteins for EVs, source of EV extraction(type of cell), lipid composition.	EVs
Toxicity	General information on the toxic effects of nanoparticles, including acute, chronic, and repeated dose toxicity measurements. Example: LD50 value in mg/kg.	All
Zeta potential	Surface charge of nanoparticles, affecting stability and aggregation, measured in millivolts (mV). Example: -30 mV.	All

of the data extracted by the LLM pipeline. It represents the codification of domain expertise, guiding the LLM’s extraction process towards scientifically meaningful information.

E. LLM-based Information Extraction Framework

The core of this thesis lies in the development and application of an LLM-based framework designed to systematically extract the nanoparticle design parameters, as defined by the taxonomy, from the preprocessed corpus of scientific literature. This framework encompassed the careful selection of appropriate LLMs, the adoption of a specific prompting strategy, the implementation of methods for handling long documents, the exploration of different strategies for aggregating information from document chunks, and a final harmonization step to refine the extracted data.

1) *Selection of Candidate Large Language Models:* Three open-weight LLMs were selected as candidates for the primary information extraction task, along with an additional judge model. The selection of these models was guided by a balance of their capabilities, accessibility, and suitability for the research objectives. The selected models were:

- 1) **Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct:** A model known for its strong performance relative to its size and its instruction-following capabilities [20].
- 2) **Qwen3 32B:** A model offering great comprehension of complex scientific texts [28].
- 3) **Gemma3 27B-it:** A model from Google, designed for robust instruction following and strong general language understanding [27].
- 4) **MedGemma 27B-text-it:** A domain-adapted variant of Gemma3 27B-it used as a judge model to harmonize and refine multi-LLM outputs [12].

Table III
OVERVIEW OF SELECTED LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS AND THEIR TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

Model Name	Params	Context Len.	Min. VRAM (FP16/BF16)
Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instr.	24B	128k	~55 GB
Qwen3 32B	32.8B	32k native / 131k (YaRN)	~65.6 GB
Gemma3 27B-it	27B	128k	~54 GB
MedGemma 27B-text-it	27B	128k	~54 GB

The key technical specifications of the selected candidate LLMs and the judge model are summarized in Table III. To streamline discussion, these models are hereafter referred to as Mistral Small, Qwen3, Gemma3, and MedGemma.

The rationale for selecting these specific models was driven by several factors:

- **Accessibility and Resource Efficiency:** These models, with sizes ranging from 24 billion to 32 billion, are notably smaller than the largest proprietary models. This characteristic makes them potentially deployable on consumer-grade Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), aligning with the aim of developing a pipeline that is more accessible to the broader research community, rather than relying on costly API access or extensive computational clusters. This choice addresses a practical limitation noted in Section II regarding the resource-intensiveness of many current LLM applications.

- **Instruction-Following Capabilities:** The "Instruct" variant of Mistral Small, and similar optimizations in Qwen3 and Gemma3, indicate that these models are specifically fine-tuned to understand and follow complex natural language instructions. This is a crucial attribute for zero-shot prompted extraction tasks, where the model’s behavior is guided entirely by the prompt [31].
- **Open-Weight Nature:** The use of open-weight models promotes transparency and reproducibility in research. It allows other researchers to potentially replicate, validate, or build upon this work using the same foundational models.
- **Architectural Diversity (Implicit):** While all are transformer-based architectures, these models originate from different research groups and development efforts. They may have subtle differences in their training data, fine-tuning processes, and underlying architectures, which could lead to variations in their strengths and weaknesses when processing and understanding specialized scientific text. The comparison of their performance therefore provides insight into the current capabilities of this class of models for domain-specific information extraction.

This selection strategy aimed to balance the pursuit of high extraction performance with the practical considerations of computational resources and the principles of open science, hence contributing to the understanding of how effectively these more accessible LLMs can perform complex, domain-specific information extraction tasks.

2) *Prompt Design and Zero-Shot Extraction Strategy:* A zero-shot prompting strategy was adopted for the information extraction task. This decision was primarily driven by the absence of a large, manually annotated dataset specific to nanoparticle design parameters that would be required for supervised fine-tuning of the LLMs or performing few-shot learning as indicated in Figure 2. The creation of such a dataset was deemed beyond the resource and time constraints of this thesis work.

Figure 2. Decision flowchart for selecting a zero-shot prompting strategy. Supervised fine-tuning and few-shot learning are not feasible when there is lack of labeled data.

- **Custom Prompt Engineering:** A single, custom-designed prompt was implemented for this task. This prompt was used uniformly across all three candidate LLMs to ensure a fair comparison of their capabilities. The prompt was structured to clearly instruct the LLMs to identify and extract values for each of the fields defined in the nanoparticle design taxonomy (see Section III-D). The prompt framed the task as requiring the LLM to act as a domain expert, carefully reading the provided scientific text and populating a predefined schema with information found within that text. It specified the desired output format and provided guidance on handling cases where information for a particular field might be absent.
- **Zero-Shot Learning Paradigm:** The LLMs were tasked with performing the extraction based solely on the instructions embedded in the prompt and their vast pre-existing knowledge acquired during their foundational training. No task-specific examples (few-shot learning) were provided within the prompt, nor was any fine-tuning performed on domain-specific annotated data. This approach makes use of the remarkable generalization capabilities of modern LLMs to new tasks when guided by well-designed prompts.
- **Structured Output Format:** The prompt explicitly instructed the LLMs to return the extracted information in a structured JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) format. Within this JSON object, the keys were designed to correspond directly to the fields outlined in the nanoparticle design taxonomy. This structured output is essential for downstream data analysis, database population, and quantitative evaluation.

In a zero-shot setting, the quality and precision of the prompt are paramount to the success of the extraction task. The prompt serves as the sole interface for guiding the LLM’s behavior. Consequently, considerable effort was invested in designing a prompt that was clear, specific, unambiguous, and comprehensive enough to elicit the desired information accurately and consistently. The effectiveness of this prompt design is, therefore, an implicit variable being evaluated alongside the LLMs themselves.

3) *Processing of Large Documents: Chunking and Context Preservation:* Scientific research articles frequently exceed the maximum context window limitations of many LLMs, including those selected for this study. To address this practical constraint, a document chunking strategy was implemented for articles whose length was prohibitive for single-pass processing by the LLMs.

- **Chunking Mechanism:** Documents identified as "very large" (i.e., exceeding a predefined token limit suitable for the chosen LLMs) were segmented into smaller, manageable text chunks.
- **Overlap Strategy:** An overlap of three sentences was maintained between consecutive chunks. For example, the last three sentences of chunk n would also form the first three sentences of chunk $n + 1$.
- **Rationale for Overlap:** The sentence overlap was implemented to preserve contextual continuity across chunk

boundaries. This is crucial because information relevant to a specific nanoparticle design parameter (e.g., its size and the method used for its measurement) might be described across a passage that happens to be split by a chunk boundary. The overlap aims to reduce the likelihood that such information is fragmented in a way that hinders the ability of the LLM to correctly interpret and extract the complete detail. Three sentences were chosen as a heuristic to balance the need for adequate context preservation against the introduction of excessive redundancy in processing.

- **Process:** Each generated chunk was then treated as an independent unit of text and was processed individually by the designated LLM using the same custom prompt designed for the extraction task.

Although chunking is a necessary technique for handling long documents with fixed-context LLMs, it introduces its own set of complexities. A key challenge is that information pertaining to a single nanoparticle design or a specific experimental detail might be distributed across multiple chunks. While the sentence overlap helps mitigate the loss of immediate local context, dependencies spanning longer distances within the document (e.g., an abbreviation defined in an early section and used extensively later) can still pose challenges. Most importantly, the generation of multiple partial extractions (one per chunk) necessitates a subsequent aggregation or merging strategy to consolidate this fragmented information into a single, coherent record for the entire document. The effectiveness of this chunking and subsequent aggregation process is therefore a key determinant of the overall pipeline’s performance, particularly for longer and more information-dense scientific articles. In this study, chunking was required for fewer than 1% of the documents, and even among those, no document exceeded two chunks—indicating that the potential impact of chunking-related fragmentation on overall extraction quality was minimal.

4) *Aggregation of Chunk-Level Extractions:* When the chunking strategy was employed for a given document, the individual JSON outputs generated by the LLM from each chunk had to be consolidated into a single, comprehensive JSON object representing the entirety of the relevant information for that document. Two distinct strategies were implemented for this aggregation task:

1) Strategy 1: First Non-Null Value Aggregation

- **Description:** This strategy involved iterating through the predefined fields of the target JSON schema. For each field (key), the final value assigned in the aggregated JSON object was taken from the JSON output of the first chunk (in sequential order of processing) that provided a non-null (i.e., not empty, missing, or explicitly stated as not found) value for that particular field.
- **Rationale:** This is a straightforward, rule-based, and computationally inexpensive approach to aggregation. It operates on the assumption that the first instance of a specific piece of information encountered by the LLM as it processes the document

sequentially is likely to be the primary or definitive statement of that information. Although simple, its main limitation is that later chunks might contain more accurate, complete, or updated/corrected information for a field, which would be ignored if an earlier chunk already provided a value. Furthermore, this method cannot synthesize or combine information that is inherently fragmented across multiple chunks (e.g., if part of a nanoparticle’s name is in one chunk and its core material in another, and the prompt expects them related).

2) Strategy 2: LLM-based Merging and Synthesis

- **Description:** In this more sophisticated approach, the individual JSON outputs from all processed chunks of a single source document were first concatenated (i.e., as a list of JSON objects). This collection of partial results was then fed as input to the candidate LLM. The LLM, when serving as a "merging agent" was provided with a specific set of instructions (a "merging prompt") guiding it to analyze these multiple partial results and synthesize a single, consolidated JSON object that best represents the complete information from the document.
- **Rationale:** This strategy aims to leverage the advanced language understanding and reasoning capabilities of an LLM to perform a more intelligent and context-aware merge. It has the potential to resolve conflicts between information found in different chunks (e.g., slightly different size values), choose the most comprehensive entry if multiple chunks report on the same parameter, or even synthesize information that is clearly related but was extracted in a fragmented manner across chunk boundaries. The main challenge with this approach is its increased computational cost (due to an additional LLM call per document) and the complexity of designing an effective merging prompt that reliably guides the LLM to produce the desired consolidated output without introducing new errors or hallucinations.

These two aggregation strategies reflect fundamentally different philosophies for consolidating information from chunked documents. The First Non-Null strategy emphasizes simplicity, speed, and reliance on the earliest reported value, making it efficient but potentially lossy. In contrast, the LLM-based Merging strategy prioritizes semantic coherence and completeness, albeit at the cost of increased computational overhead and additional prompt engineering. Ultimately, despite its higher computational cost, the LLM-based merging approach was preferred for its superior ability to synthesize and consolidate the full scope of information extracted from each document.

5) *Result Harmonization and Adjudication using a Judge Model:* To further enhance the robustness, reliability, and potential accuracy of the extracted data, a final harmonization and adjudication step was introduced into the pipeline. This step involves processing the outputs generated by the three candidate LLMs (Mistral Small, Qwen3, and Gemma3) for the same source document using a dedicated "judge" LLM.

- **Judge Model Selection:** MedGemma, a 27 billion parameter model based on Gemma3 27B-it and further fine-tuned for the medical domain, was selected for this adjudication role.
- **Rationale for Judge Model:** The selection of MedGemma was based on the hypothesis that a model with enhanced training or fine-tuning within the biomedical domain might possess a deeper understanding of medical and nanotechnological terminology, relationships, and typical data presentation styles. This domain-specific expertise could enable it to more effectively reconcile discrepancies, identify plausible values, and synthesize a more accurate consensus from the (potentially slightly differing) outputs of the general-purpose candidate LLMs.
- **Adjudication Process:** For each of the processed source document, the three distinct JSON outputs (one from each of the candidate LLM) were provided as input to the MedGemma judge model. MedGemma was then prompted with a specific set of instructions. These instructions guided the judge model to analyze the three input JSON versions, compare the values for each corresponding field, and produce a single, harmonized JSON object. The harmonization instructions include rules such as prioritizing values where there is a consensus among the input LLMs, selecting the most complete or detailed entry in cases of discrepancies, using its domain knowledge to pick the most plausible value, or flagging fields where significant disagreement or uncertainty persists (set the values of such fields to null) across the inputs.
- **Objective of Adjudication:** The adjudication step was designed to implement an ensemble-like approach to improve data quality. By leveraging the collective "wisdom" or diverse outputs of multiple extractor LLMs, the process aimed to correct errors or omissions made by individual models, recover missing information captured by only some models, and produce a final JSON output for each scientific paper that is more accurate, consistent, and reliable than any single LLM’s output alone. This multi-stage pipeline—comprising initial extraction by several models followed by domain-aware adjudication—represents a sophisticated strategy to mitigate individual model weaknesses. It is particularly valuable in complex scientific domains where ground truth is often ambiguous and expert interpretation is essential.

F. Evaluation Framework

The performance of the developed LLM-based information extraction pipeline and its various configurations is quantitatively assessed using a custom-developed Python script. The structured JSON outputs generated by the LLM pipeline is compared against the manually curated gold standard (see Section III-H1). The evaluation addresses the third research aim by providing a thorough, quantitative measure of accuracy for the extracted nanoparticle design parameters, thereby facilitating a thorough comparative analysis of different methodological choices.

Table IV
EVALUATION METRICS BY FIELD TYPE

Field Type	Metric(s)	Description
Categorical	Exact Match	Checks if the extracted value exactly matches the gold standard value.
Numeric	MAE, RMSE, Exact Match	Measures closeness of numerical values such as particle size or zeta potential. Exact match is reported when discrete values are expected.
Free Text	BERTScore (Precision, Recall, F1)	Computes semantic similarity between extracted and reference text using contextual embeddings (DeBERTa-based), suitable for descriptive fields like mechanisms or compositions.
Null Handling	Precision, Recall, F1	Evaluates the ability to correctly identify when fields should be null or non-null, capturing both hallucinations (false positives) and omissions (false negatives).

The evaluation process for each document pair (LLM output vs. gold standard) is executed in a sequence of checks:

- 1) **JSON Validity and Structure:** The LLM output is verified to ensure it is a valid JSON object.
- 2) **Schema Conformance:** Structural integrity is assessed by comparing the JSON object against a predefined master schema corresponding to the nanoparticle type. A **Schema Conformance Score** is computed as the proportion of expected fields present in the output. In addition, the evaluation identifies and reports any *missing fields* (expected but absent) and *extra fields* (present but not expected), providing insights into adherence to the required data structure.
- 3) **Field-by-Field Content and Null-Value Evaluation:** A detailed field-by-field comparison is performed. For each schema-defined field, both the extracted and gold standard values are normalized (e.g., converting placeholders like "not mentioned" to null) and evaluated in two dimensions:
 - **Null Handling Analysis:** It explicitly evaluates the LLM's ability to correctly identify the presence or absence of information. Every field is classified into one of four categories:
 - **Correct Null:** Both the LLM output and the gold standard are null.
 - **Incorrect Null (Omission):** The gold standard contains a value, but the LLM output is null.
 - **Incorrect Value (Hallucination):** The gold standard is null, but the LLM provides a value.
 - **Correctly Valued:** Both provide non-null values, pending content analysis.
 - **Content Accuracy Analysis:** For fields where both the LLM output and the gold standard contain non-null values, accuracy is assessed using metrics tailored to the data type of each field, as specified in the master schema and summarized in Table IV.

G. Calculation of Performance Metrics

Based on the multi-dimensional comparison, a comprehensive set of performance metrics is calculated. Instead of a single, generic accuracy score, the framework generates distinct metrics for structure, null handling, and content accuracy, which are calculated per-document and then aggregated.

- **Structural and Null-Handling Metrics:**
 - **Schema Conformance Score:** The average score across all documents, indicating overall structural fidelity.

- **Null-Handling Evaluation (Precision, Recall, F1-Score):** Using the classifications of Omission and Hallucination as false negatives (FN) and false positives (FP) respectively, metrics are calculated for both the "null" class (how well the model identifies fields that should be empty) and the "value" class (how well the model identifies fields that should contain data). This provides a granular view of the model's reliability.
- **Content-Specific Metrics:**
 - **Categorical Fields:** For fields with a limited set of possible values (e.g., "Nano material name", "Targeting(EV)"), performance is measured by **Exact Match Accuracy**.
 - **Numerical Fields:** For quantitative data (e.g., "Particle Concentration"), numerical values are first parsed from strings, intelligently handling ranges, scientific notation, and uncertainty markers (e.g., ' $10-20$ ', ' 3×10^{10} ', ' 10 ± 2 '). It then computes:
 - * **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** Represents the mean of the absolute differences between extracted and gold standard values.
 - * **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):** Computes the square root of the mean of the squared differences, penalizing larger errors more heavily.
 - * **Numerical Exact Match Accuracy:** Represents the proportion of numerical values that exactly match the gold standard.
 - **Free-Text Fields:** For descriptive fields such as "Composition" and "Pharmacokinetics", a simple exact match is insufficient. A **BERTScore** is employed, to measure semantic similarity. This yields:
 - * **BERTScore (Precision Recall, F1-score):** This metric computes the degree of semantic similarity between the extracted text and the gold standard, accommodating variations in phrasing.

These metrics are calculated for each file and then aggregated (e.g., using macro-averaging for per-file scores such as MAE and BERT F1, and micro-averaging for accuracy scores) to produce overall performance indicators for each pipeline configuration.

H. Comparative Analysis

The evaluation framework enables a detailed comparative analysis by processing the outputs from different pipeline configurations. These include:

- Assessing the extraction performance of each individual candidate LLM.
- Evaluating the impact of the MedGemma judge model on final accuracy by comparing the metrics of the harmonized output to those of the individual LLM outputs prior to adjudication.

This structured evaluation offers a robust and objective assessment of the LLM pipeline’s capabilities and shortcomings in retrieving complex nanoparticle design-related data from scientific publications.

1) *Gold Standard Corpus Development*: To enable the quantitative evaluation described in Section III-H, a gold standard corpus was systematically developed. This corpus serves as the ground truth against which the outputs of the LLM-based information extraction pipeline are compared.

- **Selection of Evaluation Set**: A subset of 50 scientific articles was randomly selected from the total curated corpus of 528 papers. This selection was performed using a stratified random sampling approach. The stratification aimed to ensure that the 50-paper evaluation set proportionally represented the overall corpus in terms of:
 - **Nanoparticle Type Distribution**: The proportion of papers focusing on each of the six targeted nanoparticle types (see Section III-B1) in the evaluation set mirrors their distribution in the full corpus (presented in Table I).
 - **Original Document Format Distribution**: The ratio of papers originally in PDF format versus XML format within the evaluation set was also maintained to reflect their proportions in the larger corpus. This was considered important as the initial format could influence the quality of text extracted during pre-processing, potentially impacting subsequent LLM extraction performance.

The summary of the distribution of the 50 articles in the gold standard evaluation set is given in Table V.

Table V
DISTRIBUTION OF THE GOLD STANDARD EVALUATION CORPUS BY NANOPARTICLE TYPE AND ORIGINAL DOCUMENT FORMAT (N=50).

Nanoparticle Type	PDF Count	XML Count	Total
Extracellular Vesicles	9	6	15
Lipid Nanoparticles	14	1	15
Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles	2	2	4
Metal-Organic Frameworks	1	1	2
Polymeric Micelles	9	3	12
Spherical Nucleic Acids	2	0	2
Total	37	13	50

- **Manual Annotation Process**: Each of the 50 selected articles was manually annotated by a single researcher. The annotator was tasked with carefully reading each paper and extracting the correct values for all fields defined in the nanoparticle design taxonomy (described in Section III-D). The extracted information for each paper was recorded in a structured JSON format, identical to the target output format of the LLM pipeline.
- **Annotation Guidelines**: Detailed annotation guidelines (i.e., detailed description of each field within the taxon-

omy, alongside the data type(s)) were provided to the annotator to ensure consistency in interpretation and data entry.

- **Final Gold Standard**: The result of this process is a set of 50 gold standard JSON files, each corresponding to one paper in the evaluation set, representing the definitive, manually extracted information for all targeted nanoparticle design parameters. This gold standard is the benchmark against which all LLM pipeline outputs for these 50 papers are evaluated. The statement regarding "no labelled data" in Section III-E2 referred to the unavailability of a large corpus to fine-tune the LLMs during the information extraction phase. The creation of this smaller, dedicated evaluation set became a necessity during the evaluation phase.

I. Tools and Technologies Employed

The implementation of the described methodology and the development of the computational pipeline utilized several key software tools, libraries, and computational resources:

- **Programming Language**: Python (≥ 3.9) was the primary programming language used for all custom scripting, including data retrieval, preprocessing, LLM inference, and evaluation.
- **Literature Retrieval**: The BioPython library [9], specifically its Entrez module, was utilized for programmatic access to NCBI databases for automated article retrieval.
- **PDF and XML Processing**: Mistral OCR [19] was utilized to convert PDF documents into Markdown. Standard Python libraries such as xml and the re module (for regular expressions) were used for parsing XML files and other complex string manipulations.
- **LLM Inference**: LLM interactions were managed using the HuggingFace Transformers library [32] for locally hosted models.
- **Data Handling and Analysis**: The pandas library was used for managing metadata about the document corpus. Python’s built-in json library was used extensively for handling the JSON-formatted data. NumPy was used for efficient numerical computations.
- **Evaluation Metrics Calculation**: The custom evaluation script employed several standard libraries to compute its metrics:
 - `scikit-learn`: Used in the calculation of recall, precision, and F1-scores for the null-handling analysis.
 - `bert-score`: Employed for the semantic comparison of free-text fields. This relies on the PyTorch framework and was configured to use the `microsoft/BiomedNLP-BiomedBERT-base-uncased-abstract-fulltext` [13] model for generating contextual embeddings.
- **Computational Resources**: Experiments involving LLM inference were carried out on the Mahti supercomputer within Finland’s CSC infrastructure, utilizing a single

node equipped with 4× NVIDIA Ampere A100 GPUs, each with 40GB of HBM2e memory.

- **Development Environment:** The `argparse` library was used to create a command-line interface for the evaluation script. Development and experimentation were carried out using standard tools like `VSCode` and `Jupyter Notebooks`.

IV. RESULTS

This section details the quantitative results obtained from evaluating the proposed pipeline. An evaluation was performed on a gold standard corpus of 50 scientific articles (see Section III-H1). The performance of the three candidate LLMs (Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct, Qwen3 32B, and Gemma3 27B) and the harmonized output from the MedGemma 27B judge model are reported, focusing on schema conformance, accuracy for categorical, numerical, and free-text fields, and null-handling capabilities.

A. Overall Pipeline Performance and Schema Conformance

Across all evaluated models and document types, the pipeline demonstrated excellent structural integrity. The average schema conformance score was consistently 1.0 for almost all configurations, with Gemma3 27B achieving 0.997 for XML files. This indicates that the LLMs, guided by the engineered prompt, were highly successful in generating outputs that adhered to the predefined JSON schema corresponding to the nanoparticle design taxonomy.

B. Performance of Candidate Models

The performance of the individual LLMs varied across different metrics and input document types (PDF-derived vs. XML-derived content).

1) *Performance on PDF-Derived Content (37 documents):* Table VI presents the performance of each model on 37 documents originally in PDF format, processed via Mistral OCR and preprocessed into clean markdown format. The metrics include exact match accuracy for categorical and numerical fields, BERTScore for free-text fields, null-handling F1-scores, and error metrics for numerical values.

Table VI
MODEL PERFORMANCE ON PDF-DERIVED CONTENT ACROSS MULTIPLE EVALUATION METRICS

Metric	Mistral Small	Gemma3	Qwen3
Numerical Exact Match	0.722	0.458	0.463
Categorical Exact Match	0.703	0.653	0.400
Free-text BERT F1	0.504	0.586	0.572
Null F1 (Null Class)	0.802	0.814	0.818
Null F1 (Value Class)	0.776	0.820	0.818
MAE	1.22×10^{10}	7.84×10^{10}	4.21×10^9
RMSE	1.87×10^{10}	1.55×10^{11}	7.30×10^9

2) *Performance on XML-Derived Content (13 documents):* Table VII presents the evaluation metrics for 13 documents originally in XML format, where cleaner text extraction was possible. The results show generally improved numerical fidelity compared to PDF-derived content.

Table VII
MODEL PERFORMANCE ON XML-DERIVED CONTENT ACROSS MULTIPLE EVALUATION METRICS

Metric	Mistral Small	Gemma3	Qwen3
Numerical Exact Match	0.600	0.522	0.667
Categorical Exact Match	0.467	0.433	0.321
Free-text BERT F1	0.553	0.603	0.613
Null F1 (Null Class)	0.809	0.811	0.797
Null F1 (Value Class)	0.793	0.826	0.821
MAE	18.59	17.60	11.15
RMSE	22.27	20.73	15.54

A striking observation is the disparity in MAE and RMSE for numerical fields between PDF and XML sources. For all candidate models, these error metrics were several orders of magnitude lower for XML-derived content (MAE typically < 20, RMSE < 25) compared to PDF-derived content (MAE and RMSE in the range of 10^9 to 10^{11}). This suggests that the text extraction from XML was considerably cleaner, particularly for numerical data, while OCR and parsing from PDFs likely introduced substantial errors in representing numerical values, especially those in scientific notation.

C. Performance of the MedGemma 27B Judge Model

The MedGemma model, serving as a judge to harmonize the outputs of the three candidate LLMs, demonstrated the performance shown in Table VIII.

Table VIII
PERFORMANCE OF MEDGEMMA ON PDF- AND XML-DERIVED CONTENT

Metric	PDF-Derived (37)	XML-Derived (13)
Numerical Exact Match	0.453	0.577
Categorical Exact Match	0.653	0.400
Free-text BERT F1	0.600	0.644
Null F1 (Null Class)	0.810	0.847
Null F1 (Value Class)	0.831	0.861
MAE	8.50×10^{10}	3.73×10^{11}
RMSE	1.65×10^{11}	8.35×10^{11}

For PDF documents, MedGemma’s performance in numerical and categorical exact matches was comparable to Gemma3 27B but did not surpass the higher numerical and categorical accuracy of Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct. However, MedGemma achieved a slightly higher free-text BERT F1-score (0.600) than any individual candidate model on PDFs.

For XML documents, MedGemma achieved the highest free-text BERT F1-score (0.644) and the best null-handling F1-scores. Its numerical exact match accuracy (0.577) was competitive, though lower than Qwen3 32B (0.667) and Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct (0.600). Its categorical accuracy (0.400) on XML was lower than that of Mistral Small (0.467) and Gemma3 (0.433). The MAE and RMSE for numerical fields from XML sources for MedGemma were notably higher than those of the individual candidate models, suggesting potential issues in harmonizing numerical data from XML when discrepancies arose, or that the aggregation process itself introduced some numerical distortion for XML in the judge model’s case.

Figure 3. Comparative Performance of LLMs on PDF-Derived Content. This chart visualizes key performance metrics for Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct, Gemma3 27B, Qwen3 32B, and the MedGemma 27B judge model when extracting nanoparticle design parameters from 37 documents originally in PDF format. Data corresponds to values presented in Table VI and Table VII.

Figure 4. Comparative Performance of LLMs on XML-Derived Content. This chart visualizes key performance metrics for Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct, Gemma3 27B, Qwen3 32B, and the MedGemma 27B judge model when extracting nanoparticle design parameters from 13 documents originally in XML format. Data corresponds to values presented in Table VI and Table VII.

D. Summary of Key Observations

- All models demonstrated excellent adherence to the output JSON schema.
- Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct showed strong performance in numerical and categorical exact matches for PDF-derived content.
- Qwen3 32B outperformed the others in numerical exact matches for XML-derived content and generally had the lowest MAE/RMSE for numerical data across both

document types.

- The quality of the input text significantly impacted numerical data extraction accuracy, with XML-derived content yielding substantially lower MAE and RMSE values compared to PDF-derived content, likely due to OCR and parsing challenges with scientific notation in PDFs.
- The MedGemma 27B improved the semantic similarity of free-text (BERT F1 score) for both PDF and XML content and showed the best null handling capabilities, particularly for XML. However, it did not consistently outperform the best individual candidate LLM across all exact match metrics and showed higher numerical errors for XML content.
- Null-handling F1-scores were generally robust across models (around 0.80-0.86), indicating a good capability to discern the presence or absence of information.

V. DISCUSSION

The results presented in Section IV provide valuable insights into the robustness and failure cases of employing open-weight LLMs for the automated extraction of structured data from scientific publications. This section interprets these findings, relates them to the broader context of scientific information extraction, discusses the implications for the field of nanomedicine, and acknowledges the limitations of the current study while proposing avenues for future research.

A. Interpretation of Extraction Performance

The successful adherence of all models to the predefined JSON schema (schema conformance ≈ 1.0) is a positive initial finding, demonstrating that modern LLMs can reliably produce structured output when appropriately prompted. This aligns with observations by Zhang et al. [34] regarding the suitability of LLMs for generating structured data.

The performance variation across different data types (numerical, categorical, free-text) and LLMs highlights the distinct capabilities of these models. Mistral Small 3.1 24B Instruct’s superior performance on exact match tasks for PDF documents (numerical accuracy 0.722, categorical accuracy 0.703) is noteworthy, especially considering its smaller size compared to Qwen3 32B. This suggests that model architecture and training data may play a more meaningful role than sheer parameter count for certain types of focused extraction tasks. Conversely, Qwen3 32B showed strengths in numerical extraction from cleaner XML data.

The stark difference in MAE and RMSE for numerical fields between PDF and XML sources is an important finding. The extremely high error rates for PDF-derived numerical data (MAE/RMSE in the order of 10^9 to 10^{11}) compared to XML-derived data (MAE/RMSE < 25 for candidate LLMs) strongly point towards critical challenges in the upstream OCR and text parsing stages for PDF documents. As noted in Section III, incorrect parsing of scientific notation (e.g., “ 3×10^{11} ” becoming “31011”) would lead to such inflated error metrics. This underscores that the overall pipeline’s accuracy is strongly influenced by the quality of the initial text

extraction—a challenge well documented in the literature concerning PDF document processing. Although Mistral OCR was chosen for its advanced capabilities, complex scientific layouts and notations remain a hurdle.

The free-text BERT F1-scores, ranging from approximately 0.50 to 0.64, indicate a moderate level of semantic similarity for descriptive fields. Although not perfect, these scores suggest that the LLMs can capture the essence of complex textual descriptions, which is promising for fields requiring deep comprehension. The MedGemma judge model consistently achieved the highest or near-highest BERT F1-scores, suggesting that the harmonization process was beneficial for improving the quality of free-text extractions—potentially by selecting the most coherent or comprehensive descriptions from the candidate LLMs.

Null-handling capabilities, with F1-scores generally above 0.80, are encouraging. This implies that the models are reasonably adept at identifying when information is explicitly absent or “not mentioned” in the text, thereby reducing the likelihood of hallucinating values for missing fields—a common concern with LLMs. The MedGemma judge model showed particularly strong null-handling for XML documents (F1-scores \sim 0.85–0.86).

B. Qualitative Error Analysis

To develop a more comprehensive insight into the model’s failure modes beyond aggregate metrics, a qualitative analysis of extraction errors was performed. Table IX presents illustrative examples of discrepancies between the gold standard annotations and the outputs from the MedGemma judge model. These examples highlight common challenges such as misattribution of values to incorrect fields, extraction of irrelevant or hallucinated information, over-simplification leading to loss of meaningful detail, and the tangible impacts of upstream OCR errors, particularly with numerical data and scientific notation from PDF sources.

The error patterns observed suggest areas where prompt refinement or model capabilities could be improved. Field confusion, such as extracting particle size for monodispersity, indicates a failure by the LLM to grasp the distinct semantic meaning of each field in the taxonomy. This could be addressed by refining the prompt to include more explicit negative constraints (e.g., “For the ‘Monodispersity’ field, extract only the Polydispersity Index (PDI) or descriptive terms like ‘monodisperse’, not the particle size”). Furthermore, the over-simplification of complex fields like “Material composition” into a mere list of chemicals indicates a loss of crucial relational and structural information, which is vital for understanding nanoparticle design. This points to a deeper challenge in getting LLMs to synthesize descriptive narratives. A potential mitigation strategy could involve a two-step prompting approach: a first prompt to extract key entities (core, shell, ligand, drug) followed by a second prompt that instructs the model to describe the relationships between these extracted entities. These qualitative insights complement the quantitative metrics and are essential for guiding future improvements to the extraction pipeline.

Table IX
EXAMPLES OF QUALITATIVE EXTRACTION ERRORS BY MEDGEMMA

Field Name	Source Text	Gold Standard	MedGemma Output & Explanation
Monodispersity (Homogeneity)	"...hydrodynamic diameter of 22 ± 1 nm..." (no explicit statement on monodispersity).	null	Output: " 22 ± 1 nm" Error: Field confusion: extracted size instead of monodispersity.
Particle number	"...administered intranasally at doses up to 15 mg DMH-CA/kg..."	"Administered...15 mg/kg...; effective dose 3 mg/kg."	Output: "1 mg/mL" Error: Hallucinated a concentration instead of dosage.
Nano material name	"...TMZ-loaded MNPs@MIL[b]..."	"TMZ-loaded MNPs@MIL[b]"	Output: "MNPs@MIL[b]" Error: Omitted "TMZ-loaded" prefix.
Material composition	Text detailing structure: "These hybrid nanoparticles consist of an Fe ₃ O ₄ magnetic nanoparticle (MNP) core, coated with an iron-based Metal-Organic Framework (MIL) shell... The MIL phase is suggested to be MIL-101 like... Loaded with Temozolomide (TMZ)."	"Hybrid nanoparticles consisting of a Fe ₃ O ₄ magnetic nanoparticle (MNP) core. The MNP core is coated with an iron-based Metal-Organic Framework (MIL) shell, synthesized using Fe ³⁺ (from MNPs and added FeCl ₃) and 2-aminoterephthalic acid as the organic linker. The MIL phase is suggested to be MIL-101 like and contains Cl- in its lattice. Loaded with Temozolomide (TMZ)."	Output: "Fe ₃ O ₄ , 2-aminoterephthalic acid, FeCl ₃ / Fe ³⁺ , Cl-" Error Type: Extreme Simplification / Loss of Detail. Explanation: MedGemma’s output is a list of chemical components, losing crucial structural information (core-shell nature, MIL type) and the loading with TMZ. This indicates a failure to capture the descriptive composition, possibly due to over-aggressive summarization during harmonization or a chunking issue fragmenting the full description.
Permeability	No statement confirming BBB permeability.	null	Output: "Yes" Error: Incorrect inference from general context.
Particle size (PDF)	"...particle size of 3×10^2 nm..."	"300 nm" or " 3×10^2 nm"	Output: "3102 nm" Error: OCR artifact misread scientific notation.

C. Effectiveness of the Judge Model

The introduction of the MedGemma judge model aimed to improve overall extraction quality through an ensemble-like harmonization process. The results show a mixed impact. While MedGemma enhanced free-text extraction quality (BERT F1) and null-handling, it did not consistently surpass the best individual candidate LLM in exact match accuracy. The notably high MAE/RMSE for MedGemma on XML-derived numerical data, caused by the occasional selection of an incorrect value from a candidate LLM during adjudication, is particularly concerning.

This finding suggests that while ensemble strategies are beneficial, the simple harmonization logic based on consensus or conflict-default-to-null is suboptimal and needs careful tuning. The model’s effectiveness is constrained by its adjudication rules, which may not be sufficiently refined to handle disagreements in precise numerical or categorical data. More sophisticated ensemble techniques, such as weighted voting based on a model’s known strengths for certain field types or using model-generated confidence scores to resolve conflicts, could prove more effective.

D. Comparison with Existing Literature and Research Aims

The achieved performance, particularly for categorical and numerical exact matches (ranging from 0.32 to 0.72 depending on model and data type), and free-text semantic similarity (BERT F1 0.50-0.64), demonstrates the potential of using open-weight LLMs in a zero-shot setting for this complex, domain-specific task. These results are broadly consistent with the moderate accuracies reported in other studies applying LLMs to scientific data extraction, such as Schmidt et al. [25], who reported 72-82% accuracy in systematic reviews, albeit with different tasks and proprietary models.

This study successfully developed a pipeline architecture and a detailed taxonomy, addressing two of the primary research aims. The performance evaluation provides a baseline for future work in this niche area, which has seen limited systematic efforts for comprehensive nanoparticle design extraction, especially for BBB applications. The use of open-weight models deployable on reasonably accessible hardware also addresses a gap concerning resource-constrained environments.

E. Implications for Nanomedicine Research

The development of an automated pipeline, even with its current limitations, holds promise for accelerating knowledge synthesis in nanomedicine. The ability to extract data on nanoparticle core materials, physicochemical properties, surface modifications, and experimental models from the vast body of literature into a structured taxonomy could greatly aid researchers in identifying trends, formulating hypotheses, and designing new experiments for BBB-targeting nanoparticles. This directly supports the goals of the NAP4DIVE project by providing a method to populate the database required for the ML-based simulator. However, the current accuracy levels, particularly for precise numerical data from PDFs, indicate that the LLM outputs would require human review and verification before being reliably used in meaningful downstream applications.

F. Study Limitations

Although this study offers valuable findings, there are important limitations to consider:

- **Gold Standard Quality:** The gold standard was annotated by a single researcher without establishing inter-annotator agreement (IAA). This is a notable methodological limitation, as it prevents the assessment of the ground truth's reliability and introduces the risk of subjective bias. Without measuring IAA (e.g., using Krippendorff's Alpha), it is impossible to know if extraction "errors" reflect model failure or simply a different, yet valid, interpretation from the sole annotator. This directly impacts the validity of all reported performance metrics.
- **Preprocessing Challenges:** The high MAE/RMSE for numerical data from PDFs clearly indicates that the OCR and text parsing stage was a major bottleneck. Errors in converting complex scientific notation or numbers embedded in tables would inevitably lead to poor extraction

performance, irrespective of the LLM's capabilities. The current pipeline is thus highly sensitive to the quality of upstream text conversion, and this study did not explore advanced mitigation techniques beyond using a high-quality, general-purpose OCR tool.

- **Zero-Shot Approach:** The reliance on a zero-shot prompting strategy, while pragmatic, inherently limits performance compared to what might be achievable with fine-tuned models adapted to domain-specific terminology. Although few-shot prompting was considered, it was deemed infeasible due to the context window limitations of the chosen models, which would necessitate excessive chunking and context fragmentation. The qualitative error analysis also revealed instances of hallucination and field confusion that might be mitigated with more targeted training.
- **Evaluation Corpus Size:** The evaluation was conducted on a corpus of 50 papers. Although stratified, a larger evaluation set would provide more robust and generalizable performance estimates.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This thesis designed, implemented, and evaluated a computational pipeline that leverages open-weight LLMs to extract structured nanoparticle-design data from scientific articles, with a focus on blood-brain-barrier (BBB) formulations. We (i) constructed a detailed taxonomy of BBB-relevant nanoparticle parameters, (ii) built a modular extraction pipeline centered on three candidate LLMs and a harmonization "judge model", and (iii) carried out a systematic performance evaluation.

Key findings. The pipeline shows clear promise for automating a task traditionally handled by domain experts. All three models generated JSON outputs conformant with the pre-defined schema in a zero-shot setting. Performance, however, varied by model and data source: *Mistral* performed best on categorical and numerical fields extracted from PDFs, whereas *Qwen3* led on cleaner XML content. The *MedGemma* judge improved free-text coherence and null handling, though its effect on exact-match scores for structured fields was mixed.

Impact of upstream data quality. Substantial discrepancy in numerical error rates (MAE and RMSE) between PDF-derived and XML-derived content highlights the profound impact of OCR and text parsing challenges, particularly with scientific notation in PDF documents. This finding underscores that improved preprocessing is as important as LLM choice for high-fidelity extraction.

Research objectives achieved.

- 1) *Taxonomy:* Produced a BBB-centric nanoparticle-design taxonomy.
- 2) *Pipeline:* Implemented a modular architecture featuring retrieval, preprocessing, chunking, multi-LLM extraction, and judge-led harmonisation.
- 3) *Evaluation:* Devised a robust framework that reports schema conformance, categorical accuracy, numerical error, free-text semantic quality, and null handling.

Contributions and outlook. The results of this work extend the evidence that open-weight LLMs can accelerate knowledge

synthesis in nanomedicine, albeit with human oversight still required—especially for numeric data from OCR-heavy PDFs. Limitations include a gold standard annotated by a single researcher and persistent challenges in processing scientific PDFs.

Future research should prioritize refining the gold standard via multi-expert annotation and inter-annotator agreement, improving OCR and parsing for numerical content (e.g., using multimodal models or hybrid pipelines), and exploring parameter-efficient fine-tuning (e.g., LoRA, QLoRA) to adapt LLMs to nanoparticle-specific terminology. Additionally, ensemble methods for output adjudication, confidence scoring, prompt refinement, and ontology integration are promising directions to enhance robustness, interpretability, and generalizability. Finally, expanding the pipeline’s scope to other nanomedicine domains or broader literature corpora would increase its scientific utility.

The extracted JSON outputs will populate a centralized digital nanoparticle library planned for development within the NAP4DIVE project. This library will serve as the input to a machine learning–based simulator for predicting the effectiveness of novel BBB-targeting formulations. In this way, the pipeline developed in this thesis contributes a pivotal foundation toward data-driven nanoparticle design and simulation, bridging literature mining with in silico experimentation. The journey toward fully automated, high-fidelity scientific data extraction is ongoing, but the progress made herein signifies a promising stride forward.

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CODE AVAILABILITY

All code developed as part of this thesis has been made publicly accessible at: <https://gitlab.abo.fi/nap4dive/nanoparticle-llm-extractor>

VII. APPENDIX

APPENDIX A

PROMPT TEMPLATES USED FOR EXTRACTION AND HARMONIZATION

A. Prompt for the Three Candidate LLMs

System Prompt:

You are a specialized Nanomaterial Data Annotation Bot. Your exclusive function is to parse scientific text and populate a predefined JSON schema with utmost precision.

You MUST:

- Ignore any information not directly relevant to the requested properties.
- Extract data **ONLY** for the primary nanoparticle that was evaluated for blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability.

- Prefer the specific formulation name (e.g., 'SQV-CSLNs', 'mApoE-Liposomes') over generic names (e.g., 'liposome', 'nanoparticle').
- Output **ONLY** the specified JSON object. Do not explain, summarize, or provide any output besides the JSON.

User Prompt (Template):

You are a Nanomaterial Data Annotation Specialist. Your sole task is to carefully analyze the provided scientific text and extract specific properties for the nanoparticle type: [Target Nanoparticle Type].

Your output **MUST** be a single, valid JSON object and **NOTHING ELSE**.

IMPORTANT FILTERING RULES:

- If multiple nanoparticle types or formulations are described, extract data **ONLY** for the formulation explicitly associated with **blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability** testing or results.
- Ignore any nanoparticle described in comparison, as a variant, control, or alternative if it is not explicitly evaluated for BBB permeability.
- Look for phrases like: “was tested for BBB permeability,” “crossed the BBB,” “brain delivery,” or “evaluated for BBB crossing.”
- Use the **Permeability** property to identify the nanoparticle of interest.
- Always extract the **most specific name** of the nanoparticle (e.g., 'SQV-CSLNs', 'PEGylated Doxil'), **NOT** generic class names ('liposome', 'extracellular vesicle', 'nanoparticle').

EXTRACTION RULES:

- Adhere strictly to the property keys listed below.
- If information for a property is **NOT** found, is ambiguous, or not applicable, use `null` not the string "null".
- Extract numerical values with their units **EXACTLY** as they appear (e.g., "50 nm", "-25 mV"). Preserve original precision and formatting.
- For properties expecting lists (Array datatypes), use `[]` if no data is available or for multiple distinct values.
- For morphology from figures, cite the figure (e.g., "Figure 3") if mentioned; otherwise, provide the image description or use `null`.

Target Nanoparticle Type: [Target Nanoparticle Type]

Properties to Extract (with descriptions and focus cues):

[Property Description Block]

Use this exact schema format for your output:

```
```json
[Target JSON Schema Example]
```

**Scientific Text to Analyze:**

--- TEXT START ---

[Scientific Text to Analyze]

--- TEXT END ---

REMEMBER: Your output must ONLY be the single JSON object. Do not include any explanations, comments, or extra text.

### B. Prompt for Chunk-Level Aggregation

*System Prompt:*

You are an expert assistant in nanoparticle data harmonization. Your job is to merge multiple partial JSON objects into one complete object, using expert judgment.

**Merging Rules:**

- If multiple JSON objects provide the same key:
  - Prefer the most comprehensive and informative value.
  - Do not repeat synonymous or equivalent values (e.g., "spherical" and "Spherical").
  - Do not merge with "null" or "Not specified".
  - If the same value appears multiple times (even with minor textual variations), keep only one concise, representative version.
  - Combine distinct, complementary values only if they add new, non-redundant information.
  - If values contradict each other, set the key's value to null.
  - For the same key, if one or more values are null/not given/not specified, keep the non-null value.
- Always retain units (e.g., "50 nm", "-25 mV").
- Use null if no valid information is available.
- Follow the target schema exactly — do not omit or add keys.
- Output a single JSON object only. No explanations or markdown code fences.

*User Prompt (Template):*

Avoid repeating the same information in different words or formats. Keep each value concise, representative, and informative. Below is the target schema you must follow:

[Target JSON Schema Example]

Here are the JSON objects extracted from different sections (chunks) of a scientific document on "[Nanoparticle Type]":

[List of JSON objects from chunks]

Merge the above objects into one complete JSON object according to the rules. Return only the final JSON object.

### C. Prompt for MedGemma Harmonization

*System Prompt:*

You are MedGemma, an expert AI assistant specializing in harmonizing and aggregating scientific data about nanoparticles from multiple LLM sources. Your task is to create a single, coherent JSON

object based on the `extracted_data` from three different models: Gemma, Qwen, and Mistral for the nanoparticle type: [Target Nanoparticle Type]. Adhere strictly to the provided property schema and the following aggregation rules:

**Aggregation Rules:**

- 1) **Consensus:** If two or more models agree on a value for a property (conceptually the same value), use that majority value.
- 2) **Conflict:** If all three models provide different and conflicting non-null values for a property, set that property's value to null.
- 3) **Missing Data:** If all three models report a null-equivalent value (e.g., actual null, "Not given", "Not specified", etc.) or the property is missing, set the field to null.
- 4) **Partial Agreement:**
  - If one model provides a substantive value and others are null, use the substantive value.
  - If two models provide different substantive values and one is null, use null, unless the two values are conceptually similar.
- 5) **Data Integrity:** Retain original units and precision. Do not rephrase or summarize.
- 6) **Schema Adherence:** Output MUST conform to schema. Use null if data cannot be determined.
- 7) **Null Values:** Use the JSON literal null, not the string "null".
- 8) **Scientific Notation:** Normalize values (e.g.,  $1.6e10$ ) only when unambiguous.

**Your output MUST be a single, valid JSON object and NOTHING ELSE.**

*User Prompt (Template):*

Please harmonize the `extracted_data` for the nanoparticle type: [Target Nanoparticle Type].

**Target Nanoparticle Type:** [Target Nanoparticle Type]

**Target JSON Schema Example (Your output must follow this structure for all keys):**

[Target JSON Schema Example]

**Property Definitions (for context):** [Formatted Property Definitions]

**Data from Gemma model:**

[Gemma JSON]

**Data from Qwen model:**

[Qwen JSON]

**Data from Mistral model:**

[Mistral JSON]

Apply the aggregation rules carefully to each property key. **Remember: Output ONLY the single JSON object.**

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